

A Portfolio of Policy Instruments for Carbon Dioxide Removal

1. There is a wide array of policy instruments available to govern CDR. They can broadly be grouped into overarching classes, which have different characteristics. However, each single instrument must be carefully assessed to find the best options in a specific use case.

Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) will be required at large scales to achieve national and international climate and net-zero goals. A set of diverse CDR methods is available, ranging from ecosystem-based approaches like agroforestry to novel industrial solutions like direct air carbon capture and storage (DACCS). The ambitious climate goals put forward by many jurisdictions across the world (e.g. the the German goal for greenhouse gas neutrality in 2045), and the thereby

implicit need to scale CDR methods, will not materialise without dedicated policies. A broad set of policy instruments can be utilised to govern CDR, some designed specifically for CDR, others by adjusting broader climate policy schemes towards CDR. Figure 1 provides an overview map of these instruments, which can broadly be grouped into climate policy instrument classes defined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (Gupta et al., 2007).

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The policy instrument classes differ in their characteristics. The same applies to the respective instruments, which often combine aspects of more than one class. For example, an emission trading system (ETS) may primarily be labelled a compliance market, but it may also comprise detailed regulations, accompanying information campaigns, and even aspects of subsidies (e.g. via free allowance

allocation). Thus, an evaluation of the mere classes does not suffice to get a clear picture of what CDR policy design to pursue. Instead, a detailed analysis of specific policy instruments in a given setting (e.g. environmental and social conditions, regional characteristics, policy objectives and priorities) must be carried out when designing CDR policies and selecting respective instruments.

2. Several criteria must be considered when designing policies for CDR. The PoEt Assessment Framework can structure the thinking about future CDR governance and allow for an informed decision about policy instruments.

In the policy-making process, decision makers are to consider a broad set of criteria to ensure a responsible CDR scale up that avoids negative side effects as far as possible. These criteria are rooted in governance principles (Honegger et al., 2022) and can be structured around feasibility (what can we do?) and desirability (what would be good to do according to certain values?). To allow for a structured approach towards multi-dimensional policy design, dedicated assessment frameworks can be utilised, which aim at deriving informed and balanced decisions. The Policies and Ethics (PoEt) Assessment Framework (Holland-Cunz and Baatz, 2025; see Figure 2)

was specifically designed to evaluate policy instruments for CDR. The PoEt Assessment Framework (Holland-Cunz and Baatz, 2025; see Figure 2) was specifically designed to evaluate policy instruments for CDR. It can be applied to support the policy design process (ex-ante), to evaluate an instrument's performance (ex-post) and to derive consistent reasoning for or against specific instruments. To demonstrate a potential use case of the framework, we conducted a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) analysis based on key dimensions for two theoretical, but realistic scenarios comparing different CDR policy instruments in different settings (see Table 1):

1.) Temporary subsidy as a bridge to the inclusion of CDR into an ETS: In this scenario, the EU introduces a two-way Carbon Contracts for Difference (CCfD) scheme to bridge the price gap between the EU ETS allowance (EUA) price per ton and the cost of capturing and storing a tonne of CO₂. In such a scheme, the regulator and a removal project developer agree on a strike price allowing stable revenues for the project developer. When the EUA price is below that strike price, the regulator pays out the difference to the project developer. In a two-way system as proposed here, the project developer pays the difference between EUA and strike price when the former is above

the latter. The long-term vision in this scenario is to pave the way to enable the integration of CDR into the EU ETS.

2.) Carbon Takeback Obligation (CTO) to implement the polluter pays principle: The CTO in this scenario obliges fossil fuel producers and/or suppliers across the globe to compensate every CO₂ equivalent of sold fossil fuels with an equivalent amount of captured CO₂, thereby "taking back" the emissions caused by the produced fossil fuel. In this scenario, we refer to a Carbon Storage Obligation, under which only permanently stored CO₂ qualifies to comply with the regulation.

3. Each policy instrument presents its own unique set of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats across governance dimensions. Specific circumstances (e.g. regional characteristics, political system and objectives) must be considered and instruments carefully evaluated to determine the most appropriate policy solutions in a specific use case.

The results in Table 1 below show that the two (exemplary) instruments perform differently across the dimensions:

Table 1:

Policy instrument SWOT analysis based on key dimensions of the PoEt Assessment Framework for two theoretical, but realistic scenarios (exemplary results).

	Temporary subsidy (CCfD) as a bridge to the inclusion of CDR into the EU ETS	Carbon Takeback Obligation (CTO) to implement the polluter pays principle
S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publicly acceptable (two-way system avoids windfall profits, burden shared between public and private finance) End date defined → no „open-end funding“, incentive to drive down costs Create sustainable demand-pull → scale up CDR solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Polluter pays principle Straightforward concept, likely to receive high public support Theoretically implements a net-zero anthropogenic CO₂ circle
W	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Burden on public finance and tax payers Adding subsidised mitigation options into ETS leads to interference with markets → inefficient use of mitigation options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Burden on fossil fuel producers, passed on to consumers Enables continued use of fossil fuels Does not incentivise net-negativity
O	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Functioning ETS market offers sustainable business case for CDR providers CDR scale up creates job opportunities, tax revenues etc. Offsetting opportunity for hard to abate sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers functioning business case for CDR providers Increased learning through economies of scale → potential benefits to other use cases of CDR CDR scale up creates job opportunities, tax revenues etc.
T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Later integration of CDR into ETS could lead to „emission reduction deterrence“ Failure to lower costs could lead to stranded assets (and potentially continuation of public support) Offsetting could lead to continued use of fossil fuels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global agreement potentially never reached High Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) and infrastructure requirements might hinder enforcement Low storage quality and neglecting non-CO₂ and fossil fuel-production related emissions could jeopardise net-zero goals

Source: Based on Winkler et al. (2025)

The evaluation of CDR methods and policies is complex and must account for various contextual factors. Just as there is no "silver bullet" solution among CDR methods themselves, there is also no single policy instrument that can effectively incentivise a successful CDR strategy to reach climate neutrality goals.

It is essential to recognise that the effectiveness of policy instruments – such as regulations, subsidies, taxes, information instruments, voluntary agreements or market-based mechanisms – varies depending on the method, the region, and the specific socio-political and economic conditions, and that each instrument carries its own strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

For instance, regulations might be effective in enforcing emission reductions and mandating the adoption of CDR methods in highly regulated industries, but they may be less effective in encouraging

voluntary actions by private landowners or small businesses. In contrast, subsidies and tax incentives can lower the financial barriers to entry for new CDR projects, making it easier for companies and individuals to invest in such activities. However, to maximise the instruments' effectiveness and ensure economic sustainability, they must be carefully designed and strategically applied, typically with a focus on short-term support.

Similarly, market-based mechanisms allow carbon credits generated by CDR projects to be traded, promoting cost-effective projects through competition. However, their sustainability depends on clear regulatory frameworks, robust MRV systems and market transparency to prevent issues like double counting or carbon leakage. Further, they may fail to incentivise cost-intensive and/or novel CDR methods like DACCS

4. **There is no silver-bullet solution that is universally applicable to all CDR methods or all geographical and political settings. A portfolio approach, which takes into account geographical, socio-cultural and temporal dimensions, should be a key element in a CDR strategy to mitigate potential weaknesses and address specific needs.**

Ultimately, the success of CDR policies depends on a portfolio approach that integrates multiple policy instruments, each tailored to the specific needs and capacities of different regions and sectors. Since every policy instrument has its own strengths, weaknesses,

opportunities, and threats, a combined approach is essential to complement these aspects and create a balanced strategy that maximises the benefits while minimising risks and securing broad societal support.

CONCLUSION

Scaling up CDR is required to achieve climate goals. Designing policies for CDR methods should be based on a broad set of governance principles and criteria. To choose the most appropriate options from the pool of available policy instruments, careful assessment of considered instruments in a given regional and socio-

cultural setting is key. Dedicated assessment frameworks can support the policy design to ensure a structured process and informed decisions. To balance the different instruments' strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats, a portfolio of CDR policy instruments should be implemented.

About CDR-PoEt (2021 - 2025)

Carbon Dioxide Removals – Policies and Ethics (CDR-PoEt) examines the ethical and equity implications of policy instruments for CDR, based on interdisciplinary research and stakeholder deliberations. The project specifically evaluates the feasibility ("what can we do from an economic, socio-cultural, and institutional perspective?") and the desirability ("what do we want to do?") of CDR policies and methods in their specific contexts, providing a foundation for developing policy recommendations at local, national and international levels.

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